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USE OF MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

Annotation: *This article provides information on the use of modern innovative technologies in the development of English language teaching and the development of the English language.*

Keywords: *English, method, development, lesson, lesson, learning process, information, innovation.*

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of foreign languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take a worthy place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners. " As a logical continuation of these ideas, the Presidential Decree of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. New methods and requirements for teaching foreign languages in the country have been developed in accordance with the Recommendations of the European Framework for Assessment of Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to him, textbooks have been created for students of secondary schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms are equipped with stands and new information and communication technologies. The demand for learning a foreign language is growing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, reading, listening comprehension and speaking), each of which provides specific concepts and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is invaluable. The use of technology is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. The use of modern technologies in the educational process is also an important factor for students to

be familiar with and use information and communication technologies. One of the most effective ways is to teach and learn a foreign language using modern technology. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods;
- CD players are available.

The use of these tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of games help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology is an activity that activates and accelerates the student. Psychologists say that the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of the individual to express himself, to find a stable place in life, to self-manage, to realize his potential. At the heart of any game should be generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Learning games should be based on the subjects. During the games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a normal lesson and is more comfortable. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a way of teaching. Students are interested in playful lessons, they strive to win, and the teacher uses them to educate the student. The student is interested in believing that he or she can play, speak, listen, understand, and write in English. We know that in the current educational process, the student has to be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase learning effectiveness. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods, based on the experience of United States states and English educators:

- "Creative Problem Solving" is the beginning of the story. students are referred to the student judgment;
- "Merry Riddles" Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;
- Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;
- "Warm-up exercises" to use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson;
- Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises;
- A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills;
- Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Interpreter, Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to students;
- Poets and writers such as U.Shakespeare, A.Navoi, R.Burns can be "invited". At the same time, using the words of wisdom they say in class will help young people grow up to be perfect people;
- The "When pictures speak" method is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop students' oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures;
- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately.

Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student tries to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective use of innovative technologies by future teachers. possible.

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